

Destination Development through Sustainable Tourism Management (Tanguar Haor as a Case Study)

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Abstract:

This research paper seeks to study the present status of tourism in Tanguar Haor, with a future plan to develop this Wetland destination in a Sustainable Management approach based on the needs of the local community. The aim of this paper is to draw conclusions that help to develop a Sustainable management and destination development plan for Tanguar Haor, which will ensure- long term economic viability to the Local Communities, Conservation and Sustainable Management of Natural Resources of Tanguar Haor while enhancing tourists/visitors experience as well as community well-being. This paper consists of three basic parts. Current tourism attractions, facilities, accessibility, economic contributions of Tanguar Haor are described in the first part. The second and third part respectively contains several key issues which need to be addressed for sustainable tourism development, as well as their prioritization matrix along with objectives and appropriate action plan.

The research paper endorsed continuous measurement and monitoring of output so that evaluation can be done with the success criteria of destination management action plan, to ensure sustainable development of Tourism, Tanguar Haor resources, and Community.

Key Words: Destination development, Sustainable Tourism Management, Tanguar Haor.

1. Introduction:

Bangladesh is bestowed with innumerable tourism assets. She has a hundred gates open for entrance but not one for departure. Apart from the popular and unique tourist destinations like Cox's Bazar-The longest unbroken sandy beach, St. Martin Island, Bandarban, Rangamati, Sundarban-The largest mangrove forest of the world, Kuakata, Paharpur, Mainamoti, Srimangal, Bagerhat etc., a huge tourism treasure is lying almost uncovered in the north-eastern part of Bangladesh. This area is upper Sylhet region mainly comprising with big water bodies and wetlands. Locally they are known as Haors, Baors, Beels, jheels etc.

Tanguar Haor is considered one of the largest wetland ecosystems that have been diagnosed as one of the maximum essential wetlands not best of Bangladesh but additionally of South Asia. It is one of the beautiful water bodies which has earned name internationally for its location, immensity, biodiversity, flora and fauna, heart of migratory birds, and its economic significance. It's far considered one of the most important wetland ecosystems in northeast place of Bangladesh comprising of ten thousand ha of land area. It is located in the district of Sunamgonj (25°06'-25°11' N and 91°01'-91°06' E) at the foot of the Khasi Hills and declared as an Ecologically Critical Area (9727 ha land) by the Government of Bangladesh, considering its critical condition as a result of overexploitation of its natural resources. Later, this wetland was also declared as a wetland of international importance under the Ramsar Convention in 2000.

2. Literature Review:

A substantial number of works on destination development has been done throughout the world. But relatively a few works and literatures on destination development through sustainable tourism management for wetland have been found as yet. Similarly in Bangladesh, enough literatures on the same area particularly on 'Tanguar haor' are not available. However, few articles and research reports, and publications of IUCN addressing the importance of wetland tourism in a skin-deep manner have been

available to us. As a consequence, literatures reviewed for this research paper include only a handful of papers and the few research reports. Those are following:

In recognition of the interdependence between sustainable tourism and the conservation and sustainable management of wetlands, in February 2010, United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) signed a Memorandum of Cooperation with the Secretariat of the Convention on Wetlands (www.ramsar.org). The enhanced cooperation between both organizations has been expected to facilitate the development of project proposals and joint initiatives aimed at reinforcing the role of wetlands and their biodiversity ecosystems for sustainable tourism development (UNWTO, 2010).

Wetland.Org reported that the relationship between tourism and wetlands is however complex and sometimes adversarial. Tourism can impact wetlands in a number of ways such as by causing habitat loss, pollution, noise or over-consumption of water. But with proper planning tourism can also be an innovative mechanism for funding nature conservation and development of local livelihoods.

Wetlands are important not only for their role in maintaining ecological balance and biodiversity conservation but also for their contribution in providing livelihood to a large number of people around the world. Without proper management of the wetland resources, the wetland itself can be degraded and even be ruined permanently. (IUCN, 2015)

Mr. Taleb Rifai, the UNWTO Secretary-General told “Wetlands are one of tourism’s greatest assets, attracting millions of tourists each year. Working in close partnership with the Ramsar Secretariat, UNWTO is determined to sustainably manage wetland tourism through sound policies and planning, thereby conserving them for the enjoyment of generations to come.”(Traveldailynews.com)

International tourism expenditure reached 1 trillion USD in 2011 (UNWTO press release, 7 May 2012). With half of all international tourists travelling to wetlands, especially to coastal areas, and the additional value of domestic tourism and recreational day trips, the economic value of wetland tourism is truly enormous (Ramsar and UNWTO, 2012).

On the other hand, according to the Destination Wetlands Report prepared by the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) and the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands it is estimated that half of all international tourists travel to wetlands, especially to the coast.

According to traveldailynews.com, International tourist arrivals reached 982 million in 2011 and are expected to top one billion in 2012, generating over US\$ 1 trillion in international tourism receipts. It is estimated that half of all tourists travel to wetlands, particularly coastal areas ([traveldailynews](http://traveldailynews.com), 2015).

Wetlands offer a range of recreational activities include sunbathing, swimming, boating, diving, snorkeling, sport fishing, duck hunting, photography, bird watching, and simply enjoying the landscape. Many wetlands are not just holiday destinations but are also tourist attractions themselves. (IUCN, 2015)

Wetlands sometimes play key role to the economy of a region with opportunities for revenue generation and employment. For example, in the Everglades, in the United States, this amounts to around US\$ 450 million in direct and indirect expenditures by tourists and from employment in the tourism sector. Thus tourism is an important and visible value provided by wetlands (Anand Chandrasekhar, 2013).

However, these scholarly articles, news reports, proceedings of the meetings, news clipping etc. indicate the influences of tourism in and around wetlands and similar water bodies. So, we can say that destination development in a sustainable way is expected in TH for the greater benefit of the local people and conservation of biodiversity. But a specific policy and clearly defined rules and regulations should be formed highlighting ‘dos and don’ts’ so that in a sustainable way and without hampering the ecology and biodiversity of this sensitive area we can satisfy the lust of the nature loving tourists and at the same time ensure long-term economic benefit of the local people.

3. Objectives: The objectives of the report is to develop a Sustainable Development Plan for Tanguar Haor, that will ensure-

- Sustainable monetary contribution to the nearby communities
- Conservation and sustainable management of resources of TH
- Enhance tourists/visitors experience as well as community welfare.

4. Methodology: Especially commentary method and face-to-face discussions with the locals and the stake holders were done. Beside, a focus group (includes 17 peoples) discussion became arranged where we had the chance to talk easily about the possibility of introducing sustainable tourism management there and approaches to engage the local communities as well. Moreover, we interviewed several people consisting of store keepers, motorbike drivers cum owners, boat rowers, local tour guides, villagers, and others.

5. Timing of the survey: We visited Tanguar haor from 10th-15th September 2016 (post rainy season) and 20th- 25th February 2017 (winter season), to observe two different looks of the haor.

6. PART I Situation analysis and destination audit

6.1 Seasonality: Tanguar haor noticeably has three distinct seasons: Full Flood (monsoon), Post monsoon, and winter (IUCNB, 2012).

In the course of Monsoon, water engulfs the entire of Tanguar haor excepting the small island-like settlements. Grass, reeds, and plant life all go underneath the water. They remain submerged for almost 5 months. In the post-monsoon, the water starts recessing and the visibility of submerged lands and flowers can be observed progressively. Because of mudflats, the lifestyles of the local community is tough-hit. For the duration of wintry weather, the migratory birds begin coming and the Tanguar haor turns into birds' heaven.

6.2 Tourist Attractions: Tanguar haor is a 100 sq. km wetland and 'inland sea'. The whole haor area itself is the tourist attraction for its unique characteristics and unparalleled natural setting that cannot be found in any traditionally well-known destinations in Bangladesh. As home to over 200 species of aquatic plants, 140 species of fish, 208 aboriginal bird species, 100 species of migrant birds, 34 species of reptile, and 11 species of amphibian, it is one of Asia's most magnificent natural environments. It is already a veritable Mecca for dedicated naturalists and birdwatchers as well as photographers, and those simply seeking the tranquility of such an environment. For those who did never even imagine of a boating in a sea-like water where they can see by their own eyes different species of fishes swimming in the crystal clear water while thousands of birds flying over their heads, Tanguar haor just can be a destination of 'out of this world'. This is a 'not for all' destination where only those are welcomed to explore the heavenly natural setting who have the courage to undergo all the troubles of the journey. Nature is in a very original stage there that attracts those who don't worry about facilities and services but

love to roam around the nature. Every winter Tanguar haor attracts hundred thousands of migratory birds to visit it and spend their winter there. As a result, bird-lovers and photographers follow the flock and find themselves in it. Migratory birds start to come in Tanguar haor in October, thus winter tourism also starts in October and continues till the end of March every year.

In monsoon, it looks as if an endless sea comprising all the beels and even the rivers across the haor area. Though monsoon or the rainy season extends from June to September with 80% of the annual rainfall during this period, it starts to rain early in April. All the levees or kandas (banks or higher grounds between the beels) goes under water this time and only the villages in the relatively high land can manage to remain dry but like isolated island in the endless sea. Adventure lovers, who have their dream to boat in a sea-like water body under the clouded sky that rains unpredictably, will certainly choose monsoon to visit Tanguar haor. Monsoon brings the opportunity for the tourists to observe the hardship of life of the local people living in the isolated island-like villages and working under the hard rain for livelihoods. The Hijol-Korocho

(Barringtonia acutangula and Pongamia pinnata) trees move their heads from water during rainy season that creates an unforgettable experience for

lifetime. For nature lovers, zoologists, researchers and curious minds the haor is one of the best places to observe all in one place.

The farfetched view of layers of high hills in the Indian part from Tekerhat point, Bombax Ceiba (Red silk cotton garden), the sandy Jadukata River and its origin, the view of sandy and stony river banks from Barikkar Tila and Laurer Gohr can make anyone forget the hustle and bustle of their routine life.

A village named **Indrapur** is famous for ‘**Charak Punja**’ among the ancient religion disciples, which is observed in April/May. During this festival thousands of devotees from India come to do their prayer.

6.3 Current Infrastructure and Facilities

6.3.1 Accessibility: Transportation system is not in an expected level there in Tanguar haor from the points of view of both tourists and local people. Road transportation is useful in dry season. But the main transportation mode is water transportation regardless of season.

Here table (i) and (ii) shows two different routes within/to the Tanguar haor area with the transports available. Prevailing costs of transportation are also shown in the table.

Routes	Alternative Vehicles and Fares
Sunamgonj Sadar to Solaimanpur Ghat	Three wheelers- BDT 1000, Motor bike- BDT 400-500
Solaimanpur to Golabari	Speed boat (max. 10 persons)- BDT 7000, Rowing country boats- BDT 1600-2000
Golabari to Hatirgata	Rowing country boats- BDT 1500-2000
Hatirgata to Bagalvita	Motor bike- BDT 500
Bangalvita to Jadukata River	Motor bike- BDT 450-500
To cross Jadukata River	Boat- BDT 10 (per person)
Jadukata to haor	Three wheelers- BDT 1000

Table (i): Different Routes within haor and Vehicle Available (Plan A)

Routes	Alternative Vehicles and Fares
Sunamgonj Sadar to Jadukata River	Motor Bike-BDT 250 River crossing by boat-BDT 10 per person
Jadukata River to Taker Ghat	Motor Bike-150
Taker Ghat to Tanguar Haor	Boat-BDT 1000 (for three hours)

Table (ii): Different Routes within haor and Vehicle Available (Plan B)

***To develop the Tanguar haor as an ecotourism destination, development in transportation sector is a must, but it must be eco-friendly.

6.3.2 Food and Beverage Facilities:

Though there are some restaurants in Sunamgonj district town, there is no formal establishment for food and beverage services in Tanguar Haor. The only provision for food for tourists is the food arrangement in the houseboats. Tourist groups that hire a houseboat for two or three days to roam around Tanguar haor are provided with food in the houseboat for reasonable price.

6.3.3 Accommodation: Hotels and rest houses of different ranges of facilities and prices are available in Sunamgonj District Head Quarter. Tourists may also use houseboat/boatel accommodation. But in Tanguar haor, the number of houseboat is very limited and the facilities in the houseboat are not of that standard to satisfy all types of tourists.

6.3.4 Tour Guiding Facilities: Tour Guiding facilities are available at haor area. IUCN trained 80 young people in tour guiding with a view to motivating them to take it as their profession.

6.3.5 Economic Contributions: Majority of the tourists come to it just for a day long visit as there has been no infrastructure developed to accommodate the tourists for their overnight stay. Consequently major part of the tourist money is being spent in Sunamgonj town. In a rough estimation, only around 20 million taka is retained from tourists at haor in a year. Besides, haor produces a huge amount of fish and paddy respectively in rainy season and dry season which contributes a lot to the national economy.

6.3.6 Visitor Numbers: Despite the fact that there has no data on the vacationer's arrival in this haor area, it can be assumed that every year roughly 50000 to 60000 tourists go to this wetland. Additionally it can also be said that majority of the travelers are researchers and migratory birds watchers. Majority of the travelers go to Tanguar haor during wintry weather season with a prime goal to watch birds and to enjoy the natural beauties. The local community told that the ratio of vacationers as per winter and monsoon seasons is sort of 7:3.

7. PART II Identification of issues and prioritisation for intervention

7.1 Issues and causes: Following are the ten identified issues need to be addressed for the development of Tanguar haor in a sustainable management way:

- I. **Poor tourism infrastructure & tourist facilities:** Often tourists face the problems related with their accommodation and restaurant services.
- II. **Deficient tourism bodies and related stakeholders in the current tourism development and management:** For sustainable management and development of a particular tourist destination it is mandatory to integrate related tourism bodies and stakeholders. But in case of Tanguar haor lack of tourism bodies and related stakeholders are found.
- III. **Low conservation awareness** does not influence or inspire the tourists/local communities to save the natural environment of the destination.
- IV. **Lack of safety and security:** Though safety and security of tourists is very vital for tourism business, the boat transportation of Tanguar haor area is not secured enough for the tourists which creates high level of risk.
- V. **Poor pre-travel and on site information availability** of Tanguar haor deject potential tourists to visit. Moreover, the on-site information of this destination is also poor, which disappoints the tourists who want to visit the destination properly.
- VI. **Overfishing** has put the environment of haor under great pressure. The stock and density of fish in the shallow water is decreasing tremendously due to the combination of overexploitation and climatic changes.
- VII. **Littering** causes to environmental pollution of haor. The water vehicles which carry visitors/tourists contaminate the water by throwing out waste or garbage in the haor. Those ships/steamer boats make loud noises which disturbs the natural life of habitats as well as the harmful gases, emitted from those water vehicles drastically pollutes air environment.
- VIII. **Benefits for local community are not enhanced**

- IX. **Lack of technical support and assistance for local community** to gain benefit from tourism
The global code of ethics (UNWTO), Article 5 says- “Tourism, a beneficial activity for host countries and communities”. But in Tanguar haor, benefits from tourism for local community are not enhanced as there is no technical support and assistance for local community to gain benefit from tourism.
- X. **Absence of monitoring resources:** Though resources protection of any destination is essential, there is no system to protect the haor resources.

7.2 Prioritization matrix:

A prioritization matrix of those identified issues has been prepared on the basis of the importance. Following table portrays the prioritization of the identified issues:

Answer	Low	Med.	High	Issues									
Score	1	2	3	Poor tourism infrastructure & facilities	Deficient Of tourism bodies, related stakeholders in tourism development & management	Low conservation awareness	Lack of safety & security (Boat. T)	Poor information availability (pre-travel & on site)	Overfishing	Littering	Local community benefit is not improved	Lack Of technical skills & assistance to local community	Absence of monitoring resources
Is it easy to alleviate the issue?				2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Will alleviation of the issue show good results?				3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	3
Is solution required urgently?				3	3	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	2
Is there necessary equipment to act against the issue?				1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2
Is there staff trained to deal with the issue?				2	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	1
Will the visitor experience be enhanced if issue is removed?				3	3	2	3	3	3	3	1	3	1
Will the site image be enhanced if the issue is removed?				3	1	2	3	3	3	3	2	1	2
Is it easy to identify probable impacts of the issue?				3	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	1	2
Will the benefit to the site be greater than estimated costs of removing the issue?				2	2	1	3	2	2	3	2	1	2
Total				22	19	18	22	21	20	23	19	17	17
Priority: 21-23: 1 st 18-20: 2 nd 17 or less: 3 rd				1 st	2 nd	2 nd	1 st	1 st	2 nd	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	3 rd

Table (iii) Prioritization matrix of identified issues for Tanguar haor

8. PART III Strategic vision, Goal, Objectives, and Action plan

8.1 Strategic vision: The proposed destination management plan reflects strategic vision for sustainable development. The strategic vision for Tanguar haor is: “Improved ecosystem quality through conservation of natural resources, wetland, water resources of haor and biodiversity hotspots, and enhance multiple service benefits of ecosystems with active participation of people, dependent on natural resources for their livelihood”

8.2 Goal: In line with the vision 2022, the goal of the development plan of Tanguar haor is to present a unique destination experience to visitors, by improving ecotourism, tourism infrastructure and facilities with particular focus on the needs of the environment, the local community and the visitors; which altogether will contribute to the sustainable growth of tourism in Tanguar haor.

8.3 Objectives: Following are the objectives set for the tanguar haor Management action plan to achieve within the next six years (2017-2022). The objectives are set according to the priorities identified in the earlier section.

Objectives

8.4 Key Stakeholders and contributory roles: Development of tourism of ‘Tanguar haor’ through sustainable managerial approach can’t be achieved without the multi-level stakeholders approach. Each of the related stakeholders should embrace their responsibilities in order to work together with harmony to achieve the common goal (UNWTO, 2007). Following is the list (***) of key stakeholders who need to be involved in the sustainable tourism development process for Tanguar haor with a view to a) reducing

pollution from tourism activities, particularly by ensuring that all liquid and solid wastes are properly treated and disposed of in ways that do not result in damaging biodiversity, b) ensuring all food stuffs, and other natural assets used in tourism from sustainably managed sources; c) sustaining biodiversity protection by govt. organizations and NGOs through practical actions and plans including financial contributions, d) assuring that no insidious alien species are introduced through tourism; e) ensuring that no endangered genus are put at risk from the tourism supply chain; and f) using the communications and marketing strengths of the tourism sector to raise awareness of tourists and destination authorities of the value of biodiversity and the steps they can take to protect it.

Ministry of Water Resources (MoWR), Bangladesh Haor & Wetland Development Department (BHWDD), Bangladesh Ministry of Environment and Forest (MoEF)
Bangladesh Ministry of Civil Aviation and Tourism (MoCAT), Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock (MoFL), Ministry of Labor and Employment (MoLE), Bangladesh Ministry of Law (MoL), Bangladesh Ministry of Finance (MoF), Department of Forest (DoF) Bangladesh, Bangladesh Parjatan (tourism) Corporation (BPC), Tour Operators Association in Bangladesh (TOAB), Law enforcement Agencies (Bangladesh Police), Local Government and Community, Accommodation Service Providers near to TH Area, Boat-Owners association in TH area

**key stakeholders

8.5 Action Plan: To address the identified prioritized issues and to reach the objectives set out above for sustainable tourism development of Tanguar haor, a 6 year (during 2017-2022) action plan has been prepared and the related stakeholders identified and their contributory actions and roles outlined.

Action Plan 2017-2022

Objectives (according to priority)	Action	Responsibility	Main output/Success criteria	Time frame
Tourism infrastructure and facilities development (Code: TIFD)	<p>TIFD1: Development of travel information centre (TIC), tourists/visitors entry station, observation towers, hides, vendors, shades and resting place, trails and paths on the popular and other spots according to the visitor flow and by following the environment friendly design</p> <p>TIFD2: Upgrade and repair existing guest houses.</p>	<p>TIFD1: MoCAT, MoEF, MoWR with partnership with Private organizations</p>	<p>☒ Visitor experience will be enhanced</p> <p>☒ Uncontrolled visitation will be controlled</p> <p>☒ Visitor negative impacts on environment will be mitigated</p>	<p>TIFD1: 2017-2022</p> <p>TIFD2: By 2018-ongoing</p>
Safety and security measures for tourists in transportation (boat) (Code: SST)	<p>SST1: Develop the provision of compulsory safety and security measures in boat transportations to carry visitors in TH areas.</p> <p>SST2: Enforcement of the safety and security law through boats, ships associations, terminal authorities, and law enforcement agencies to all boats, and ships taking visitors to TH especially during Rainy Season.</p> <p>SST3: Strict action against the law breakers including fine and punishment</p> <p>SST4: Regular monitoring program to ensure the law is in action</p>	<p>SST1 MoEF, MoCAT, MoL, Local Boat and ships owners associations</p> <p>SST2-SST4: Law enforcement agencies, and Local government</p>	<p>☒ Safety and security of the visitors will be achieved</p>	<p>SST1: By 2017-ongoing</p> <p>SST2-SST4: From2017-ongoing</p>
Improvement of pre-travel and on site information availability (Code: IIA)	<p>IIA1: Provision for all related stakeholders to disseminate sufficient information to tourist via their websites, brochures, leaflets</p> <p>IIA2: Develop visitor information centres in Sunamgonj district.</p> <p>IIA3: Provide signs and interpretation, maps, conservation and environmental protection message on the popular sites and ecotourism spots</p>	<p>IIA1: MoCAT, TOAB, boats, ship associations, local government</p> <p>IIA2-IIA3: MoCAT, BPC, MoEF, BHWDD</p>	<p>☒ On-site information availability, conservation awareness will be improved</p>	<p>IIA1-IIA2: By 2017-ongoing</p> <p>IIA3: By 2018-ongoing</p> <p>IIA4-IIA5: By 2018-ongoing</p>
Reducing littering (Code: RL)	<p>RL1: Provide bins</p> <p>RL2: Provide sign and maps for location of the bins</p> <p>RL3: Introduce recycling bins</p> <p>RL4: introduce daily waste collection system</p> <p>RL5: Waste management education program for visitors, management staffs: reduce, recycle</p>	<p>RL1: MoEF, BHWDD.</p> <p>RL2: MoCAT, (BPC)</p> <p>RL3-RL4: DoE</p> <p>RL5: MoCAT, MoWR, NGOs</p> <p>RL6: MoCAT, MoEF, NGOs with cooperation with national,</p>	<p>☒ Threats on TH ecosystem will be mitigated</p> <p>☒ Visible litter will be reduce</p> <p>☒ Visitor experience will be improved & site image will</p>	<p>RL1-RL4: By 2017-ongoing</p> <p>RL5: 6 workshops and seminar in a year up to 2018 then 4 workshops and seminar up to 2019</p>

	RL6: Educate visitors to put litter on provided bins	regional and local medias.	be enhanced	RL6: From 2017-ongoing
Co-management committee for tourism development & management (Code: CCTDM)	CCTDM: Formation of the co-management committee (CMC) with the participation of tourism bodies and related stakeholders for tourism development and management in TH areas.	CCDMT: MoCAT, MoWR, BHWDD, BPC, TOAB, Local boats, ship associations, local government, local communities	☑ Sustainable tourism management in TH area will be achieved	CCDMT: By 2017-ongoing
Increase conservation & environmental awareness to local community, visitors, and management (Code: ICA)	ICA1: Educating programs and workshops for local community, management, stakeholders, and visitors regarding the importance, value of conservation ICA2: Conservation and environmental awareness programs in the national media. ICA3: Increase of signs, posts in Upazilla, tourism spots with conservation, persuasive messages	ICA1: CMC, NGOs, MoWR, BHWDD. ICA2: MoCAT, MoWR with the assistance of national electronic, print medias ICA3: MoCAT, BPC, BHWDD	☑ Conservation and environment protection for TH Areas will be enhanced in the national, regional, local, and stakeholders level	ICA1: 6 workshops in a year up to 2018 then 3 workshops in a year up to 2019 ICA2: Intensive awareness program up to 2018 then on regular interval up to 2020 ICA3: By 2018-ongoing
Increase the density of fish in shallow water (Code: IDF)	IDF 1: Creating Awareness for Fish Conservation IDF 2: Organizing training program for Local fisherman and fish producers	IDF 1: MoWR, BHWDD, MoFL	☑ The density of Fish in shallow water will be increased and the water environment for fish production will be upright.	IDF 1: 4 training program for fisherman in each year. IDF 2: Several awareness campaigns for fish conservation. IDF 3: Organizing 6 workshop for fish producers on fish production education
Increase employment opportunity for local community (Code: IOLC)	IOLC1: Training program for local community to become eco guide IOLC2: Coordination with boat operators, tour operators to hire trained eco guides from local	IOLC1: BPC, CMC, NGO IOLC2: CMC, boat operators,	☑ Employment opportunity of local community will be improved as trained eco guide	IOLC1: Yearly 3 batches for group of 35 from 2018-ongoing IOLC2: After completion of training for 1 st Batch in

	community	TOAB		IOLC1-ongoing
Technical assistance and support for local community (Code: TAS)	<p>TAS1: Provide training and technical assistance as capacity building program to run the micro enterprises more effectively</p> <p>TSA2: Provide micro financing to local enterprises to provide services for tourism.</p>	<p>TAS1: NGOs, BPC, CMC</p> <p>TSA2: Ministry of Finance (MoF), NGOs</p>	<p>☑ Local community’s technical knowledge will be improved to run their tourism micro enterprises effectively</p> <p>☑ Problem of lack of capital to run the micro enterprises to serve the tourists/visitors will be mitigated</p>	<p>TAS1: 4 training batches in every year from 2017-ongoing</p> <p>TAS2: From 2018-ongoing</p>
Develop and execute monitoring system (Code: DEM)	<p>DEM1: Formation of a Monitoring security body (to protect the environment, water and wetland resources against uncontrolled visitation, illegal activities of local community, tourist</p> <p>DEM2: Develop regular monitoring program to protect the environment, forest resources</p>	<p>DEM1: BHWDD, Law enforcement agencies, CMC, local community</p> <p>DME2: MoCAT with the assistance form MoWR</p>	<p>☑ Site resource protection will be improved</p> <p>☑ Controlled visitation of the visitors will improved</p>	<p>DEM1: By 2017</p> <p>DEM2: After DEM1 execution-ongoing</p>

Table (iv): Destination development action plan for Tanguar haor

9. Conclusion

Tanguar haor, as yet, can be termed as the virgin tourism treasure of Bangladesh. As bird watching is becoming a popular tourism event in Bangladesh. Boating through huge waters of the picturesque haor during monsoon can be turned into a very attractive tourism exercise for the sunlust tourists. Therefore it has the prospect of offering tourism services in both the seasons. Furthermore, retaining in mind the ecological and environmental troubles, we can introduce some modern facilities and points of interest for the vacationers, which include plant life and fauna museums within the haor location. Expansion of tourism spans will create opportunities for the local community to be involved in additional economic activities. This will enhance the extent of their life style and standard of residing. For this purpose, motivating and involving the local people in tourism activities, creating area-wise community based tourism organizations, management of tourism organizations and activities, empowering the tourism organizations, identifying the tourism activities, developing short term and long term touristic zones etc. are inexorable.

Most significantly, this haor should be declared as an exclusive protected tourist zone where, no tourist should be allowed to enter and roam into haor area without the help and guidance of trained guides. It will reduce scope for pollution. The tour operators also have to work in close liaison with the local guides and the local administrative body for the sustainable development of Tanguar haor.

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